

Lesu

also known as “New Ireland”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Oceanic Religions

This entry focuses on the people of Lesu (the name for both village and its inhabitants) around the time of 1930. The village of Lesu is located on the east coast of New Ireland, Papua New Guinea. At this time, the village was the largest social unit within New Ireland, and each village functioned independently. Within Lesu were 15 smaller hamlets, each containing two to eight houses. Cutting across local divisions were two exogamous moieties, the Hawk (Telenga) and the Eagle (Kongkong), which were each subdivided into several matrilineal clans. The clan was the primary economic unit and basis of political structure; important old men formed an informal council that held governing authority. Overall, Lesu religion appears to have been based primarily upon magical beliefs and practices. Although a belief in the afterlife was present, previously human spirits were not particularly involved with the day-to-day life of humans. Ceremonial activity centered around life-cycle events (such as birth, initiation of boys, first menstruation of girls, marriage, and death) and include dances and feasts. Magicians served as religious practitioners, specializing in a particular type of magic such as love, medicine, or rain. Magicians were not involved in a formal priesthood but were instead individuals who were paid for their services and held associated prestige. According to Hortense Powdermaker (1933), the principal ethnographic authority, Lesu religious beliefs and practices are “not embodied in any one institution (such as a church), but [are] instead diffused throughout all of life, and is an attitude as well as behavior” (p. 306). Because religion permeates all aspects of society, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself.

Date Range: 1915 CE - 1940 CE

Region: Lesu village, New Ireland, ca.1930

Region tags: Oceania, Melanesia, Papua New Guinea,
New Ireland

Lesu village, New Ireland, ca.1930

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. (2004). Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=om24-001>
- Source 1 Description: Powdermaker, H. (1933). *Life in Lesu: the study of a Melanesian Society in New Ireland*. W. W. Norton & Company, Inc.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=om24-002>
- Source 2 Description: Powdermaker, H. (1931). Mortuary rites in New Ireland (Bismarck Archipelago). *Oceania*, Vol. 2, 26–43.
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=om24-000>
- Source 3 Description: Levinson, D. (2012). Culture Summary: Lesu. Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Missionaries are mentioned by the principal ethnographic authority; for example: "to-day, however, it would be considered dangerous to eat a snake, because of the part it played in the Garden of Eden story, as told by the missionaries. In some vague and unexplainable way the snake is now considered a taboo food, even among unmissionized natives. They may not have accepted any of the Christian morals or tenets, or even know much about them, but the snake story they take seriously, and it is the snake which stands out as a prominent part of the Fall of Man" (Powdermaker, 1933:185). "Under the influence of Christian missionaries, Christian beliefs came to coexist with traditional ones" (Levinson, 2012).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: "Even the newly missionized native, as far as I could observe, is not a heretic. His Christian beliefs form a superficial and upper layer laid over his own beliefs, which are not denied. The two systems simply exist on different levels, and neither meet nor conflict" (Powdermaker, 1933:324).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), "internal warfare seems to be absent or rare" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), "external warfare seems to be absent or rare" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale,

2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: "Religion is both a set of beliefs and a series of acts; but in [a society such as] Lesu, it is not embodied in any one institution (such as a church), but is instead diffused throughout all of life, and is an attitude as well as behaviour" (Powdermaker, 1933:306). Based on this information, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the Lesu society itself.

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: "Religion is both a set of beliefs and a series of acts; but in [a society such as] Lesu, it is not embodied in any one institution (such as a church), but is instead diffused throughout all of life, and is an attitude as well as behaviour" (Powdermaker, 1933:306). Based on this information, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the Lesu society itself.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the Lesu would actively proselytize and recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "Religion is both a set of beliefs and a series of acts; but in [a society such as] Lesu, it is not embodied in any one institution (such as a church), but is instead diffused throughout all of life, and is an attitude as well as behaviour" (Powdermaker, 1933:306). Based on this information, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the Lesu society itself. In this way, religion has official political support.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates a conception of apostasy in the Lesu.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 232

Notes: "Lesu, the village where I lived, has 232 inhabitants, and stretches along the coast for about three miles" (Powdermaker, 1933:31).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Both men and women are magicians, although the former predominate. In Lesu there are thirteen people practising magic of one kind or another, and only two are women" (Powdermaker, 1933:297). "The thirteen magicians of Lesu form no separate class, and except for the additional prestige and income they receive they cannot be differentiated from other people" (ibid, p.298).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates a hierarchy among magical practitioners.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "Magical knowledge is inherited, and the rule is that it be handed down in the female line, and thus stays within the clan. But in tracing how each magician received his magic, I found that it came just as often from a father as a maternal uncle or other clan relative" (Powdermaker, 1933:297).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: "Magical knowledge is inherited, and the rule is that it be handed down in the female line, and thus stays within the clan. But in tracing how each magician received his magic, I found that it came just as often from a father as a maternal uncle or other clan relative" (Powdermaker, 1933:297).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: See Powdermaker, 1933:297

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: "A magician makes a payment to the person teaching him the spells, and thereafter he guards his knowledge carefully, for as has already been shown the knowledge of magic is an economic asset. Only one type of magic is usually known to a magician; for example, the rain magician will not know love magic. The exception is medical magic, which is more widely known, and so a man who is skilled in love spells may also know a few spells connected with medicine" (Powdermaker, 1933:297).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of scripture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "The native's beliefs about after life and his identification with it are not so clear. A ghost is supposed to emerge from the mouth of the dying individual, to continue living in some vague unknown manner after the individual dies" (Powdermaker, 1933:307). "It is not until after the burial rites that the element of fear enters into the emotional attitude. There is now the fear of a ghost or *tinuato*, mentioned in the beginning of this paper. After the burial of the body, it is supposed to wander around near its former habitation and to make its presence known by a low whistle" (Powdermaker, 1931:40).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The native's beliefs about after life and his identification with it are not so clear. A ghost is supposed to emerge from the mouth of the dying individual, to continue living in some vague unknown manner after the individual dies" (Powdermaker, 1933:307).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Cremation rather than burial was formerly practised, but as far as could be learned there has been no change in the rites. In the past the body was burned and the bones buried. The cemeteries existed then just as they do to-day—each hamlet with its own. In the rites to-day cremation is simply omitted and the whole body is buried instead of just the bones, as in the past" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

Cremation:

– No

Notes: "Cremation rather than burial was formerly practised, but as far as could be learned there has been no change in the rites. In the past the body was burned and the bones buried. The cemeteries existed then just as they do to-day—each hamlet with its own. In the rites to-day cremation is simply omitted and the whole body is buried instead of just the bones, as in the past" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Cremation rather than burial was formerly practised, but as far as could be learned there has been no change in the rites. In the past the body was burned and the bones buried. The cemeteries existed then just as they do to-day—each hamlet with its own. In the rites to-day cremation is simply omitted and the whole body is buried instead of just the bones, as in the past" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: "Some time in the interval preceding burial the corpse is put in its coffin, usually an old canoe with the pointed ends removed" (Powdermaker, 1931:31).

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates that corpses would be exposed to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates that the dead were fed to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment (original scale), "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of co-sacrifices in burials.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of grave goods.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: For a complete description of funerary practices and mortuary rites see Powdermaker, 1933:308-315; and Powdermaker, 1931.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cenotaphs.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "Cremation rather than burial was formerly practised, but as far as could be learned there has been no change in the rites. In the past the body was burned and the bones buried.

The cemeteries existed then just as they do to-day—each hamlet with its own. In the rites to-day cremation is simply omitted and the whole body is buried instead of just the bones, as in the past" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: The deceased are buried in cemeteries (Powdermaker, 1931:28); no ethnographic evidence indicates the deceased were interred in domestic spaces.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "There is no belief in life after death (except for the ghost), in rewards or punishments, or in any deity" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: "There is no belief in life after death (except for the ghost), in rewards or punishments, or in any deity" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Although previously human spirits are present, these supernatural beings are not described in extensive ethnographic detail. "It is not until after the burial rites that the element of fear enters into the emotional attitude. There is now the fear of a ghost or tinuato, mentioned in the beginning of this paper. After the burial of the body, it is supposed to wander around near its former habitation and to make its presence known by a low whistle" (Powdermaker, 1931:40).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "In the war and fishing magic particularly there are invocations to the ghosts of dead clan relatives to assist in fishing and in weakening the enemy" (Powdermaker,

1933:307).

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– No

Notes: "There is no belief in life after death (except for the ghost), in rewards or punishments, or in any deity" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of mixed human-divine beings.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– No

Notes: The only type of supernatural being described is human spirits. "There is no belief in life after death (except for the ghost), in rewards or punishments, or in any deity" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: "There is no belief in life after death (except for the ghost), in rewards or punishments, or in any deity" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: "There is no belief in life after death (except for the ghost), in rewards or punishments, or in any deity" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: "There is no belief in life after death (except for the ghost), in rewards or punishments, or in any deity" (Powdermaker, 1931:28).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: "During this period [of pregnancy] the pregnant woman has no sexual intercourse, either with her husband or anyone else. Her husband, however, is permitted to have sexual relations with other women" (Powdermaker, 1933:63).

Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: "During this period [of pregnancy] the pregnant woman has no sexual intercourse, either with her husband or anyone else. Her husband, however, is permitted to have sexual relations with other women" (Powdermaker, 1933:63).

Monogamy (females):

– I don't know

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: "It is not only through the performance of the proper rites and by feeding and caring for the infant that the duties of the parents towards the infant are fulfilled, but they must also observe certain sexual taboos during this period of infancy, when the mother is nursing her child, which lasts from two to three years. During this time the mother and her husband are not supposed to have any sexual relations with each other, or with anyone else" (Powdermaker, 1933:78).

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: "During this period [of pregnancy] the pregnant woman has no sexual intercourse, either with her husband or anyone else. Her husband, however, is permitted to have sexual relations with other women" (Powdermaker, 1933:63).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– I don't know

Notes: Ceremonies are held at significant life-cycle events such as birth, initiation/puberty, marriage, and death. These ceremonies typically involve dancing and feasts. However, it does not appear that participation in these events is mandatory. For a more detailed description of these events see Powdermaker (1933).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The Lesu have no levels of political hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands or villages. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas column 32: Jurisdictional Hierarchy (Murdock, 1967). "The village, with its distinct round of life, its chief, its important old men, its communal rites, its communally owned ground, its gossip and mass of trivial details which make up life, is the largest functioning unit based on locality...The village is subdivided into hamlets. Lesu, the village where I lived, has 232 inhabitants, and stretches along the coast for about three miles. It is divided into fifteen hamlets, separated from one another by fences and sometimes also by unused land. Each hamlet contains from two to eight houses" (Powdermaker, 1933:31). "Cutting across the local groupings are the lines of kinship. The society is divided into two exogamous moieties, Telenga, the fish hawk... and Kongkong, the eagle...The members of each moiety regard themselves as related to each other in a classificatory manner. Each moiety is divided into a number of clans, an extended family group, all the members of which are related in the female line" (Powdermaker, 1933:33). "Since it is the important old men of the clan who are the real governing force, the clan largely conditions the political structure. These men are called orang, which may be translated as old men of influence, rather than chief. It is they who are an informal council, meeting in the men's house and discussing and deciding any questions of importance" (Powdermaker, 1933:40).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a formal education system.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004), food storage is not present.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004), food storage is not present.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Tuden and Marshall (1972) column 10, Police (note, equivalent to SCCS variable 90, Police) indicates that "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery."

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Tuden and Marshall (1972) Column 9, Judiciary, indicates that "supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community."

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1-Writing and Records, the Lesu implemented mnemonic devices (Murdock and Provost, 1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Lesu rely predominantly upon agriculture (horticulture) and fishing for subsistence. Hunting and animal husbandry supplement the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Lesu rely predominantly upon agriculture (horticulture) and fishing for subsistence. Hunting and animal husbandry supplement the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.